

Consumer Electronics

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Abstract

Consumer electronics refers to any device containing an electronic circuit board that is intended for everyday use by individuals. This encompasses a massive category of electronic that includes telephone, cameras. To save staff in sales offices and control offices where reservations are processed and space on aircraft controlled. To improve the load factor on flights. Consumers look forward to connected devices that provide superior user experience.

Electronics sector has shifted from primary public sector to private sector and has immense growth opportunities.

Its total contribution to economy and sales is ever increasing.

Contribution in creating employment opportunities.

Keywords: Cell phone, DVD players, E-mail, paper shredders, Remote control, computer.

Introduction

Consumer electronics (CE) refers to any electronic devices designed to be purchase and used by end users or consumer for daily and non-commercial/ professional purposes .consumer electronics are among the most commonly used form of electronic, computing and communication devices. consumer electronics refers to any device containing an electronic circuit board that is intended for everyday use by individuals .this encompasses a massive category of electronic that includes telephone, cameras, digital cameras, PDAs, calculators, VCRs, DVDs, clocks, audio devices, headphone, tablets, smart phones and many other home products. The Blu-ray disc technology can store sound and video while maintaining high quality and also access the stored content in an easy-to-use-way.

Objective

- To improve the service given to passengers and potential passengers.
- To save staff in sales offices and control offices where reservations are processed and space on aircraft controlled.
- To improve the load factor on flights.

Overview

- Consumer looks forward to connected devices that provide superior user experience
- Constantly challenged by rapidly-evolving consumer requirements and BYOD concepts

- lot and cloud are become the back-bone of consumer electronics devices
- Technology and its adoption across the wide range of consumer electronics has evolved rapidly in recent year.

Sub Categories

- A) Audio equipment manufacturers (38c)
- C) Consumer electronics retails (2c, 21p)
- D) Dash board head units (7p)
- H) Home automation (6c, 71p)
- S) Set-top box (45p)

History

Its first fifty years the phonograph turntable did not use electronics; the needle and sound horn were purely mechanical technologies. How were, in the 1920 radio broadcasting become the basis of mass production of radio receivers. The vacuum tubes that had made radio practical were used with record players as well, to amplify the sound so that it could be played through a loudspeaker. Television was soon invented, but remained insignificant in the consumer market until the 1950.

Classification of Consumer Electronics

- Video equipment
- Audio equipment
- Home computers
- Video and electronic games
- Telephones
- Calculators and watches

Import and Export Table

Year	Export	Import	Balance
1978	1.352	0.021	1.331
1980	2.047	0.038	2.009
1983	2.829	0.020	2.809
1986	2.940	0.032	2.908
1989	2.287	0.145	2.142
1990	2.618	0.113	2.505

Benefit

We strongly believe in the convenience and flexibility offered by connected consumer electronic devices. We take pride in offering hardware and design prototypes for CE devices. Global offers OEMs and lot solution provider these advantages.

Consumer Electronics Market Size

Year	Market Size
2012	206
2013	203
2014	211
2015	285
2016	287

It is however, the fastest moving segments and consequentially development times are the shortest.

Aesthetics are paramount considerations in addition to safety, efficiency, and excellent heat management aspects according to chandler et al.(2009)

Current News (2019)

- BPL returns to flip kart to sell consumer electronics.
- Whirlpool plans Rs.590 cores capes for next 5 years.
- Slow moving consumer goods four quarters in recovery.
- Enter of newer players expanding males grooming market.
- Drenched in sweet Sony's new wearable AC will keep you in the head.

Conclusion

- Electronics sector has shifted from primary public sector to private sector and has immense growth opportunities.
- Its total contribution to economy and sales is ever increasing.
- Contribution in creating employment opportunities.
- Rivalries among firms are moderate.
- Changing lifestyle and increasing income is a stimulus for its growth.

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